

A Robust Research Data Infrastructure for the SyNergy Excellence Cluster

Advancing FAIR Data Use in Neuroscience

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Abstract: The Munich Cluster for Systems Neurology (SyNergy) investigates shared mechanisms underlying neurological disorders such as Alzheimer’s disease, stroke, and multiple sclerosis. To promote data accessibility and reuse, SyNergy developed the SyNergy Research Data Management (SyNergy^{RDM}) portal, a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data infrastructure. SyNergy^{RDM} integrates menoci, an open-source software for creating resource catalogues for publications, mouse lines and antibodies, with FAIRDOME-SEEK, an open-source platform for structured documentation of omics datasets. Hosted at the Leibniz Supercomputing Center (LRZ), it ensures secure storage, automated backups, and seamless data sharing across the cluster. Currently hosting thousands of data assets, SyNergy^{RDM} aims to enhance collaboration, transparency, and reproducibility in systems neuroscience research. It serves as a scalable model for FAIR data management and a case study for research data management (RDM) in action.

Keywords: Research Data Platform, FAIR Data Management, SyNergy Excellence Cluster, Neuroscience Research, menoci, FAIRDOME-SEEK

1. Background and Introduction

Neurological disorders are becoming increasingly prevalent, posing significant challenges to the aging population worldwide. The Munich Cluster for Systems Neurology (SyNergy) [1] is an Excellence Cluster funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) since 2012, dedicated to investigating the underlying mechanisms of complex neurological conditions, including Alzheimer’s disease, stroke, and multiple sclerosis. While these disorders present with distinct symptoms, they share common pathological processes—such as immune system activation in neurodegenerative diseases and inflammation-driven neuronal damage. SyNergy adopts a systems neurology approach, integrating insights from multiple disciplines to identify shared pathways in neurovascular, neurodegenerative and neuroimmunological diseases, and pave the way for innovative translational solutions. Given the significant effort and investment required to generate complex biological data, such as single cell sequencing datasets from valuable human disease samples, ensuring its reuse is not just beneficial but also essential for the wider scientific community. To address this, SyNergy has established a comprehensive Research Data Management (RDM) portal to ensure data integrity, storage and long-term accessibility.

The SyNergy Research Data Management (SyNergy^{RDM}) portal [2] is aligned with the GO-FAIR principles to ensure FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data management [3,4], and serves as the central hub for managing, sharing, and accessing research data across

the cluster. Hosted at the Leibniz Supercomputing Center (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities [5], it ensures transparency and collaboration across research groups by facilitating access to both published and unpublished data, through specialized databases for different data types and resources.

2. Elements of SyNergy^{RDM}

A key component of this integrated platform is based on *menoci* [6], an open-source web portal software that provides modules for cataloging of key research resources such as mouse lines, antibodies and publications. It has been successfully used in other research consortia, such as the TRR274 [7], to create intuitive, searchable resource catalogs that allow researchers to easily access and organize essential data assets. Complementing the *menoci* database, we have integrated FAIRDOME-SEEK—an open-source data management platform developed by the FAIRDOME community [8]—that is designed for detailed documentation of research workflows [9,10]. Using the Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) framework, FAIRDOME-SEEK enables structured representation of experimental data, ensuring that data sets are well-annotated, reproducible, and interoperable. This flexibility makes it particularly valuable for managing complex, high-throughput datasets generated in fields such as single cell and spatial transcriptomics or proteomics. These datasets are generated using field specific protocols and processed with standard pipelines, all of which can be documented as standard operating procedures (SOPs) on FAIRDOME-SEEK and linked to relevant assays. This ensures that datasets processed in different studies are comparable and that results are reproducible. To maximize findability of the data, we employ MIAME [11] and SDRF [12] guidelines for omics data to collect metadata on FAIRDOME-SEEK through user-defined sample type templates. The platform also supports cross-linking research data to external omics repositories such as GEO [13,14] and PRIDE [15], ensuring integration with widely used community data standards.

In addition to *menoci* and FAIRDOME-SEEK, a public webpage has been established to provide an indexed overview of relevant GitHub repositories linked to SyNergy projects, facilitating easier access to software tools and code resources developed within the cluster. Through SyNergy^{RDM}, we have also implemented data management guidelines and provided training for projects of the cluster with the following elements: (i) a dedicated data policy specifying best practices, regulations and responsibilities for annotating, storing, sharing and publishing research data; (ii) workshops and seminars on data management for researchers; and (iii) documentation for using the portal as well as external resources for RDM.

3. Data Storage, Sharing and Security

The local SyNergy^{RDM} infrastructure at all participating institutions is based on RAID [16] systems to reduce the risk of data loss, alongside automated backup or archiving through secured servers to ensure traceability of scientific results for up to 10 years (as mandated by the DFG guidelines on Good Scientific Practice). This is achieved in collaboration with the LRZ, which is connected to all hosting institutes via ultra-fast glass fiber connections within the “Munich Science Network” (MWN) [17]. Additionally, the LRZ offers flexible and scalable options to expand data storage for the SyNergy’s FAIRDOME-SEEK platform through its Data Science Storage (DSS) system, supporting the upload and secure sharing of data-intensive files such as raw and processed omics data sets. For efficient data sharing within the cluster and with external collaborators, we utilize Globus [18], a high-performance data transfer service. It allows easy integration with FAIRDOME-SEEK and seamless sharing of large datasets, while ensuring compliance with data security standards. In collaboration with SyNergy’s specialized omics technology hubs, we have established protocols for handling omics data, ensuring a streamlined process from data generation to storage in SyNergy’s DSS container.

4. Conclusion and Future Directions

SyNergy^{RDM} exemplifies an effective and scalable model for promoting FAIR data management and advancing data reuse in the systems neuroscience research community. By leveraging community-developed tools like menoci and FAIRDOME-SEEK and integrating secure services such as the LRZ and Globus for data storage and sharing, SyNergy^{RDM} offers a robust infrastructure that supports collaborative, transparent, and reproducible research. The portal currently hosts more than 2900 publications, 2500 antibodies and 300 mouse lines on menoci, and over 90 published (publicly available) and 30 unpublished omics datasets on FAIRDOME-SEEK. SyNergy^{RDM} as a use case demonstrates the benefits of a well-integrated RDM infrastructure in action, providing valuable resources for both SyNergy and the broader scientific community—ultimately accelerating discovery in systems neurology.

Moving forward, we plan to include the OMERO platform [19] as another component of SyNergy^{RDM}, to support management of imaging datasets. Developed and maintained by the Open Microscopy Environment (OME) [20] team, OMERO (OME Remote Objects) is an open-source client-server platform for managing, analyzing and sharing scientific imaging data and metadata. Particularly useful for microscopy data, it enables researchers to store, visualize, and annotate large-scale imaging datasets while supporting a wide range of file formats. OMERO also provides tools for secure data access and integration with third-party analysis software and is widely used in life sciences to facilitate collaborative research. SyNergy's OMERO instance is currently under development—and we aim to define specific use cases in the near future, which would be followed by a SyNergy-wide release.

Through regular data collection and platform updates, we expect to consistently add new assets and tools to expand the SyNergy^{RDM} infrastructure. At the same time, through our ongoing scientific communication efforts, we hope to increase awareness and accessibility of available data and RDM resources for researchers.

Resources

SyNergy^{RDM} Portal:

<https://www.synergy-munich.de/research/data-management-sharing/3e575bdc4a8c41e8>

Provides access to:

SyNergy's **Resource Catalogs (menoci platform)** <https://menoci.synergy-munich.de/>:

- Centralized inventory of >2,900 publications, >2,500 antibodies, and >300 mouse lines, fostering resource discoverability and collaboration
- Provides contact points (research groups) within SyNergy for accessing specific resources

SyNergy's **Omics Database (FAIRDOME-SEEK platform)** <https://seek.synergy-munich.de/>:

- Structures and documents omics datasets (e.g., transcriptomics, proteomics) using the Investigation-Study-Assay (ISA) standard
- Enables standardized metadata documentation for reproducibility and cross-study comparisons
- Enables secure data sharing across the cluster and external repositories (e.g., GEO, PRIDE), and cross-referencing with internal protocols and data files

SyNergy's **GitHub Repositories** <https://munich-cluster-for-systems-neurology.github.io/SyNergy-GitHub-Index/>:

- Index of public repositories showcasing analysis workflows and linked publications
- Promotes open science and collaboration by making computational tools widely available

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